

TITLE: Glucocorticoid Receptor Activation Confirms Steroid Handling via Cell-based Luciferase Assay.

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INTRODUCTION:

We recently published a study in *Science Signaling* establishing the G protein coupling profile of the adhesion GPCR, GPR97/ADGRG3 and demonstrated that the receptor is activated by its tethered peptide agonist to facilitate ex vivo human and mouse neutrophil polarization and chemokinetic migration (1). Prior to our work, the only agonists posited to activate GPR97/ADGRG3 were beclomethasone-related corticosteroids (2, 3). We tested beclomethasone alongside a GPR97/ADGRG3 tethered agonist (TA) peptidomimetic and an established ADGRG subfamily small molecule agonist (3- α -DOG) in multiple orthogonal signaling assays and neutrophil functional tests (1). Beclomethasone provided no ability to activate the receptor in any of these assays, whereas the TA peptidomimetic and 3- α -DOG did so consistently. The validity of our work was called into question with a claim that our laboratory may not have properly solubilized steroids and handled them incorrectly in the aqueous biochemical and cell-based assays. Our procedures for handling 3- α -DOG and the more difficult to solubilize TA peptidomimetic were identical to the way that we handled the steroids. To dispel this aspersion, we present a post-publication HEK293T cell-based Glucocorticoid Response Element Luciferase (GRE-LUC) assay demonstrating glucocorticoid activation of the endogenous glucocorticoid receptor (GR) that is present in the cells (4). This assay format is highly similar to the HEK293T cell-based serum response element (SRE)- and cyclic AMP response element (CRE)-Luciferase assays that we used to assign the TA peptidomimetic and 3- α -DOG, but not beclomethasone as GPR97/ADGRG3 agonists (1).

RESULT:

Dexamethasone (DEX) and beclomethasone (BCM) activated the endogenous GR in HEK293T cells in a concentration-dependent manner, producing sigmoidal dose-response curves. DEX was slightly more potent than BCM, with EC_{50} values of 1.05 nM and 3.07 nM, respectively. Maximal efficacy was similar for both GR full agonists. Co-treatment of the cells with either corticosteroid (100 nM ea.) and the glucocorticoid receptor antagonist RU-486 (1 μ M) markedly reduced GRE reporter activation, confirming receptor-dependent signaling (4, 5). Our observed measures of DEX and BCM potencies for the GR are in line with published values (6, 7).

Stimulation of Endogenous Glucocorticoid Receptor in HEK293T Cells

METHOD:

Low-passage HEK293T cells (ATCC CRL-3216) were seeded at 1.0×10^7 cells per 15 cm dish in DMEM supplemented with 10% (v/v) FBS (DMEM-FBS), 24 h prior to transfection. Cells were transfected using polyethylenimine (PEI) with a plasmid mixture consisting of 22.2 μ g pcDNA3.1, 6.85 μ g p Δ TAT₃ luciferase reporter (8), and 82.5 ng phRLuc-N1 (PerkinElmer), for a total of 29.13 μ g DNA per transfection. 6 h post-transfection, cells were detached using 0.05% (w/v) trypsin in Puck's Saline G containing 1 mM EGTA (PSG-EGTA), washed in DMEM-FBS, and cryo-preserved as aliquots in DMEM-FBS containing 10% v/v DMSO. For assays, thawed cells were plated into white, sterile, tissue culture-treated 96-well plates (BrandTech BRAND) at a density of 40,000 cells per well in serum-free DMEM. After 16 h, the medium was aspirated and replaced with 100 μ L of fresh serum-free DMEM for compound treatments. Beclomethasone (Cayman Chemical Item No. 33196) or dexamethasone (Cayman Chemical Item No. 11015) or the antagonist RU-486 (mifepristone, Cayman Chemical Item No. 10006317) were solubilized in anhydrous DMSO and serially diluted with rapid mixing into 25 $^{\circ}$ C serum-free DMEM to create 50X stocks of the appropriate concentrations. The 50X stocks were then

mixed into the medium overlaying the cells and incubated for 4h. Final DMSO concentrations were kept $\leq 1\%$ v/v. Following incubation, the plates were centrifuged at 500 g for 5 min, and 52 μ L of medium was removed. Cells were lysed by adding 50 μ L of Steady-Glo reagent (Promega), and luminescence was measured using a TriStar2 plate reader (Berthold Technologies) (9). Subsequently, 100 μ L of Renilla luciferase buffer (1.1 M NaCl, 2.2 mM EDTA, 0.44 mg/mL BSA, 0.22 M KH_2PO_4 , pH 5.1) containing 3 μ M coelenterazine h was added to each well to quantify Renilla luciferase activity (10). Data were expressed as the ratio of firefly luciferase (Fluc) to Renilla luciferase (RLuc) signals.

CONCLUSION:

Use of the HEK293T GRE-Luciferase assay affirms the ability of our laboratory to solubilize and handle corticosteroids. We observed DEX and BCM concentration-dependent activation of the GRE-LUC reporter with values that are in-line with previously published potencies, while demonstrating antagonist blockade with RU-486 (5-7). These procedures mirrored those used in our recent GPR97/ADGRG3 assays, where we demonstrated that DEX and BCM failed to engage GPR97 signaling (1). These observations with GPR97 in our orthogonal biochemical, cell line, and primary cell-based assays cannot be attributed to technical mishandling of steroids, validating our conclusion that the glucocorticoids do not activate GPR97.

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